

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Vyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University

Sole Author

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“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
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Brief Biography of Author

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

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Research practitioners, PhD researchers, Postdoctoral researchers, scientists, vice-chancellors, pro-vice-chancellors, chancellors, research directors, PhD professionals, doctoral industry professionals, university registrars/directors, PhD assessors, doctoral assessors, research professors, Nobel prize organization, Nobel prize assessors, editor of the journals, reviewer of the journals/publishing companies, research scholarship winners, research fellowship winners, criminologists, barristers, human rights professionals, professionals in public administration, law researchers, policy-makers, defence and security professionals, researchers in textile technology, researchers in color engineering, researchers in camouflage engineering, and relevant professional communities. The titles and keynotes of the articles of individual chapters and individual online links will guide and support to find the relevant articles for the relevant professional readers, writers, practitioners, and researchers.

31 December 2025

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)¹⁻⁶ is a self-funded professional reader, self-funded professional writer, independent writer and researcher, self-funded research practitioner, and self-funded research publisher since 2006 who is asking research fund of chief professor/chief scientist category to the universities/countries

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Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)³; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre³; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; research product branded as Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)²; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre²; fund approved by City University; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh.

Chief Researcher and Founder (self-funded)¹; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre¹; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, 40, Kemal Ataturk Avenue, Banani, Dhaka 1213, Bangladesh

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Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing and searching the fund in terms of following roles of senior professor/chief professor/chief scientist in technical textiles, camouflage technology, and color technology

- Chief Professor (reader/general study/PhD study/Postdoc study in camouflage, color, and textile technology) (Hossain, 2023f, 2023g)
- Chief Professor (research)
- Chief Professor (peer review and promotion of scientist/professor)
- Chief Professor (magistracy in higher education and research)
- Chief Professor (BSc thesis/MSc thesis/BTech thesis/MTech thesis/MPhil thesis/PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis/ job promotion thesis in textile technology)
- Chief Professor and Founder, department of technical textiles
- Chief Professor and Founder, department of color and camouflage technology
- Chief Professor/Chief Scientist and Founder; textiles, color, and material research centre
- Chancellor/Chief Vice-chancellor/Vice-chancellor; research and innovation

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) is proposing and searching the fund in terms of following roles of senior professor/chief professor in law and criminology

- Chief Professor (reader, general study/PhD study/Postdoc study in law and criminology) (Hossain, 2023f, 2023g)
- Chief Professor (research)
- Chief Professor (peer review and promotion of professor)
- Chief Professor/Vice-chancellor/Chancellor (magistracy in higher education and research)
- Chief Professor (academic law and professional law)
- Chief Professor (Bachelor thesis/Master thesis/MPhil thesis/PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis/job promotion thesis in law and criminology)
- Chief Professor/Chief Scientist and Founder; defence and law research centre
- Chancellor/Chief Vice-chancellor/Vice-chancellor; research and innovation

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)

R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court,

31 December 2025

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high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Professional excellency of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry,
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Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.
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Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>

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Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

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Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.

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Cite the book

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 31 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; (e-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au)

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1 Introduction

The research and development of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) has multidimensional themes of professional reading, professional writing, research, and publications which are the attraction of global research funding (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024x). He also concentrated on two-dimensional research and development in criminology versus peace. One theme of criminology denotes and focuses on defence technology and camouflage physics (Hossain, 2023g). Another theme of criminology focuses on law and global policy-making for the peace in PhD schooling; law and global policy-making for peace surviving (Hossain, 2023f). Hence, the article has a graphical abstract of the research themes and research progress in the relevant field aligned with the global themes and global peace of research and development (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ap; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (**Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ck, 2023cl**) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi,

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2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu, 2023bv; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025k; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025) (Hossain, 2015b, 2018, 2023bq, 2023br).

1.1 Keywords

Criminology, defence, science and technology, law, PhD education, PhD research, PhD scholarship, PhD school, peace in PhD schooling, global peace, PhD obstacle, PhD harassment, PhD corruption, PhD struggling, society contribution, family struggling for education, PhD struggling, dress code, life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.

2 Graphical abstract

Figure 1. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) generated a self-supervised and self-funded contribution in multidimensional

Anowar

31 December 2025

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh);
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

field of research and publication since 2006 which are totally aligned with the global themes of vibrant philosophy in contradiction with the global themes of development and surviving technique in the planet. He is a one-piece monogram/symbol for global peace. He is a one-piece blessing for the global survival technique for the peace survival technique.

3 Keynote of invention at PhD school for the peace of PhD schooling; global themes of academia, scientists, researchers, and universities; a global tune of research and development.

This is a PhD harassment report about pursuing PhD in color engineering. This harassment thesis is entitled “Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace of PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency of higher education to pursue PhD in color engineering entitled camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds”. This PhD is funded by Australian Government RTP stipend scholarship. This PhD is also self-funded and self-invested around 1800000 USD (in words eighteen lakh USD) under the Australian compliance of salary of resource person category, PhD researcher category, technologist category, scientist category and professor category. This part of PhD harassment of PhD in color engineering has contributions in criminology, international law, higher education, and PhD research.

Every PhD school is an ethical platform to achieve a PhD degree. PhD education, PhD scholarship, PhD research, and PhD achievement are the vibrant segments for society development, society contribution, and invention for the peace of mankind all over the world. Human brain engineering in the PhD platform, researcher practices, PhD practices, professor practices, scientist practices, and technological inventions are the quality dedication for the peace of mankind. These are the symptoms for increasing of human lifetime and human protection in terms of quality survival. The safety of researchers and the safety of scientists are the global challenge for the right motivation of inventions and inventors. The conspiracy of life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, PhD harassment, and PhD corruption are the obstacle to quality PhD education in an ethical platform of PhD schooling when a PhD researcher invests their ‘young time’ for a PhD degree. The PhD researcher gets a minimum amount of honorary salary in the name of PhD scholarship in the name of PhD honour. The case letters and reports of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in PhD journey have a significant contribution for every consideration of the quality PhD schooling. PhD school may influence for highest climbing and highest platform for global standardization of global PhD schooling. The conspiracy of hidden life-threatening, unethical PhD suspension, and unethical cancellation of PhD enrolment has been practically exemplified and focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school. In this author’s contribution, the PhD struggling and the PhD journey have new contribution for PhD researchers and PhD supervisors for practicing an ethical PhD in

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PhD school. This is an academic platform of Australian PhD school at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. A real-life history of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school have been signified, coalesced, and published for society contribution, excellency in higher education, and self-protection of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University investigated officially with author's family office at home country in Bangladesh of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under the verbal declaration and threatening at PhD school. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye of PhD school also communicated with former academic office of author and former professional office of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain at home and abroad under the verbal declaration and threatening at PhD school. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye of PhD school also communicated with the ambulance team of PhD candidate. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye also communicated with the emergency medical team of PhD candidate at St. Vincent hospital in Melbourne, Australia. The misuse of cyber technology also used for personal monitoring of PhD researcher in PhD school. This philosophy of critical conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment has direct impact for the protection of whole mankind, especially for the peace in PhD schooling, criminology, and human rights. The misuse of brain engineering in a prestigious PhD research platform and the misuse of technology in a prestigious PhD research platform are the artificial warning signs of academic and professional crime which are significantly stated against the peace in PhD schooling against the global ethics of brain engineering. Definitely, every schooling platform is being expanded and expanded into the global platform for civilized nature of human beings. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a lot of reporting about conspiracy of life-threatening in Australian PhD school, PhD harassment, academic and professional motivation for the peace of mankind for the peace of global PhD schooling. Subsequently, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified about his family office, former academic office, and former professional office to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice-Chancellor, President, and Chief Delegates, RMIT University to satisfy Australian Quality of Research Framework in PhD school to satisfy the verbal order of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and Professor Dr. Lijing Wang in prestigious PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Therefore, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University tried to kill Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate. Hence, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye also tried to robber the intellectual property of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. This is an official environment of PhD Schooling in an official and ethical platform of teaching-learning and brain engineering/criminal action of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye.

Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a study addicted person from child schooling to PhD schooling. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066 has completed PhD

31 December 2025

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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requirement by sole-author PhD research & sole-author PhD publication, supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang & Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain continued his full-time PhD research, his full scholarship period PhD research at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Md. Anowar Hossain faced life-threatening conspiracy in Melbourne in PhD school. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye acted as planning director, conspiracy director, financial director, trafficking director and executive director for the killing conspiracy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was able to present and submit a complete PhD thesis for his confirmation of PhD candidature in 2020-2021. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye also announced 'Nobel Nominee of Vice-Chancellor, RMIT University on behalf of Martin G. Bean, Vice-Chancellor, RMIT University, year 2020-2021. Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain successfully completed the requirements of his PhD (Fashion & Textiles) concentrated on color engineering, camouflage engineering and camouflage textiles. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye tried to kill PhD candidate, tried to cease intellectual property of PhD candidate, tried to kill the PhD dream and tried to kill the self-motivation of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under an official act of hidden life-threatening in Australian PhD school. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also studied and practiced on PhD in criminology at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when he defended against the official act of hidden life-threatening at PhD school under the registered PhD research on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). The life-threatening history was officially notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice-Chancellor, RMIT University and the whole concern of RMIT University, the whole concern of Australian community and the global community under Australian Quality of Research Framework. The PhD degree was accomplished under non-compliance harassment and motivation such as completing the first milestone and second milestone without revision and negative comments under congratulation and positive comments, number of action and support-2, artificial hampering of PhD progress, verbal threatening and PhD harassment in different ways, continuous conspiracy of life-threatening to Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, unethical executive suspension, psychologist bullying in PhD school, 100% neglecting and non-responding to life-threatening bullying of Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD school connection with psychologist, immoral cancellation of PhD enrolment and forwarded to the Victorian Ombudsman. Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to the Victorian police station, reported to the National Security of Australia, reported to the Australian Institute of Criminology, reported to the Australian Federal Police, reported to the Country Court of Australia, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to the High Court of Australia, reported to the Australian Bar Association, reported to Australian Education Department, reported to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government, reported to the minister and delegates of Australian Home Affairs, reported to Australian Foreign Affairs, reported to the Victoria Legal Aid, reported to the Australian Competition and Consumer Commission, reported

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to Australian Human Rights Commission, reported to the Human Rights commission of Bangladesh, reported to the International Human Rights, and different related organizations of different countries. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was fully unable to fight with Australian court and/or international court due to financial hardship. A report of a life-threatening conspiracy was also submitted to the Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat; submitted to the office of Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh; the High Commissioner of Bangladesh to Australia; the Governor-General of the Commonwealth of Australia, Mr. David Hurley AC DSC (Retd); reported to the Prime Minister of Australia; reported to the Chief Advisor and President of Bangladesh; reported to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations; submitted to the Nobel prize organization for Nobel prize nomination about life-threatening of reporting of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate. Unfortunately, the life-threatening/conspiracy of killing the PhD candidate issue was intentionally converted to the cancellation of material approval for PhD research & PhD progress-2021, high risk misconduct, executive suspension-2022, psychologist bullying-2023 and cancellation of PhD enrolment-2023. A full scholarship payment was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of research allowance was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of time allowance was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of office allowance was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of scholarly allowance was not provided to PhD candidate. Hence, the paid scholarship was around 252666AUD including tuition/professor's fees, the nonpaid scholarship was around 36426AUD and the nonpaid salary was around 249209AUD for artificial financial harassment of research progress at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested around 1800000 USD (in words eighteen lakh USD) for his self-sacrifice and self-earning under Australian Compliance in Australian PhD School in Australia. 50% income support and 100% life-safety support for compensations were requested and proposed to Vice-Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. 9450000USD (in words ninety-four lakhs and fifty thousand USD) was proposed and requested for 50% income support compensation. 22680000USD (in words two crore twenty-six lakhs and eighty thousand USD) was proposed and requested for 100% life-safety compensation. Every correspondence of PhD contribution, conspiracy of life-threatening, PhD harassment was forwarded, officially recorded, and officially registered to the office of Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice-Chancellor, RMIT University (vc@rmit.edu.au); the office of PhD school; all concerned offices at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; and all concerned offices of government of Australia. Occurrence and motivation of PhD schooling was also mentioned in the report of "Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform". This article is a PhD schooling harassment at RMIT University under proceeding to the registry of High Court of Australia, recommended or insinuated by the Victorian ombudsman of Australia, RMIT

Handwritten signature

31 December 2025

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 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)^{2*}
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia

International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
 Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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University of Australia and Department of Education, Government of Australia. High of court of Australia is also making a legal cost harassment to PhD candidate. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking to the Australian High Court to pay 8390000 Australian penalty units (230,72,50,000AUD). (Hossain, 2023f, 2023g, 2023ar, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf) (Hossain, 2023e, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bl, 2023bo; Hossain, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cm, 2023cn) (Hossain, 2023f, 2023g, 2023ar, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bl) (Hossain, 2023a, 2023at, 2023av, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bm, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bx, 2023by; Hossain, 2023c; Hossain, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ch, 2023cj, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024u, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Hossain, 2025a, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025j, 2025k).

4 Key methodologies for the sustainable goal of research and development

- Criminology of defence science and technology, figure 2(Hossain, 2023f).
- Criminology of law in research, PhD, Postdoc, organizational, situational, professional, and human resource, figure 2(Hossain, 2023g).

Figure 2. General methodologies and key points for the sustainable goal of research and development.

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

5 Life-time research contribution, research achievement, and research progress for approving research fund/research centre; research questions and research plans, figure 1

Figure 1, due to facing life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) parallelly analyzed and highlighted real life defence, family defence, and official defence in his PhD journey at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Australia (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ap; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (**Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ck, 2023cl**) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu, 2023bv; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025k; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025).

- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on criminology and technology; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on criminology and technology which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a, 2024f).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on criminology and law; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on criminology and law which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f, 2023g).

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Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
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 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on environmental science and technology; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on environmental science and technology which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(A. Hossain, 2020; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; Hossain, 2019d; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on Australian court and/or international court; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on Australian court and/or international court to establish legal support of researchers all over the world which is/are the major theme/themes of global research and development, figure 1 (Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023a, 2023c, 2023e; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024j, 2024x; Hossain, 2025a).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on legal acts and global policy-making; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on legal acts and global policy-making to researcher community and PhD industries which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023at; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024s; Hossain, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on the support to the research scholar in global platform of higher education, research, research law, professor (Dr.), and scientist (Dr.); the author would like to focus on support and scholarly dedications to the research scholar in the global platform of higher education, research, research law, professor (Dr.), and scientist (Dr.) which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024o, 2024p, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v; Hossain, 2025g) (Hossain, 2023e, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023av, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi; Hossain, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024d, 2024m; Hossain, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on professional reading, professional developing, and professional investing the money of fellowship and scholarship; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on professional reading, professional developing, and professional investing the money of fellowship and scholarship to win Nobel prize in peace and/or camouflage physics and/or criminology in technology and law which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f, 2023g).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on defence and security; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on defence and security which are the major themes of

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global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a).

- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on government and democracy; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on government and democracy which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024w; Hossain, 2025e).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on health; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on health which is a major theme of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023bk).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on PhD history, public administration, and public policy; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on history, public administration, and public policy which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024k; Hossain, 2025a, 2025e, 2025h, 2025i).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on migration, displacement, refugee, war, and global friendship of higher education and research; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on migration, displacement, refugees, war, and global friendship of higher education and research which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023bw, 2025g, 2025h).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on sex, women, and gender; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on sex, women, and gender which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024s).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on research scholarship and research funding; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on research funding, research scholarship, dedicate the research, acknowledge the research, and scholarly outcomes of global research and development which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023bd, 2023bo).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on PhD and Postdoc policy; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on PhD and Postdoc policy which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023f, 2025i).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on economics and currency inflation; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on economics and currency inflation which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2025e).
- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on family law; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate on family law which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc).

Anowar

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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- Author solely focuses and scholarly dedicates on academic law, research law, law of human rights; the author would like to focus and satisfactorily dedicate on academic law, research law, law of human rights which are the major themes of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023a, 2023aw, 2023bm, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023by; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024e, 2024k, 2024n; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025j, 2025k).
- Author solely focuses and dedicates on lifelong safety of researchers and scientists; the author would like to focus and scholarly dedicate to ensure lifelong safety of researchers and scientists which is a major theme of global research and development, figure 1(Hossain, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi).

Every PhD and Postdoctoral dissertation should be a sellable and profitable business to the scholar to the achiever under the administrative protocol of a government and/or university. A minimum of 100USD payment policy of each university to a PhD and Postdoc achiever may solve may glorify may certify the life-time financial solution and/or research fund of a scholar. Moreover, no university/no organization/no person will issue single dollar without cash benefit. Moreover, every PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis should be notified, circulated, recorded, registered with each university all over the world for the support of global research and development for the support of knowledge transfer under the ministry of education under the judicial support of governments under the research wings of the United Nations. Who should take care the policy? Who should administer the policy? By biological nature, every person wants a cash benefit/ready benefit rather than a complex benefit rather than circular benefit for surviving in the real society in the planet. Every government should allow a percentage of inflation to purchase a PhD and Postdoctoral thesis if the scholar has a ready contribution in thesis has a ready investment/cash investment to generate a thesis; the policy will satisfy the global transparency in research and development. This is not a matter of 100% scholarly donation if the scholar/achiever has no cash money for surviving in the society in the planet. Without which, what should be the financial strategy/achievement of the research scholarship? Without which, what should be the financial strategy/achievement of the research student? Without which, what should be the financial strategy/achievement of the university researcher? Without which, what should be the financial strategy/achievement of the PhD/Postdoc achiever? Without which, what should be the financial strategy/achievement of the university? A PhD and Postdoc should have a contribution and routine earning policy rather than the policy of routine certification. A PhD and Postdoc should not only be the symptom of routine certification if PhD and Postdoc are the symptoms of professional identity and dignity. Who is take caring the situation in the global platform of higher education and research? Who should scholarly control the situation in the global platform of higher education and research? A research/PhD thesis/Postdoc thesis should not only be the matter of journal publication without the valid earning policy/routine earning policy of a scholar/PhD achiever/Postdoc achiever.

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Possibly, still now; there is lacking of policy to satisfy the valid earning policy/routine earning policy of achiever of PhD/Postdoc thesis. Possibly, still now; there is a symptom of a joking situation with the scholar/professor/researcher/achiever. It is valid necessary; it is urgent necessary to modify to improve to transparent to suggest to glorify to signify the policy in higher education and research for global surviving. A killing conspiracy and scholarly harassment should not be the routine gift/routine earning policy for the scholar/professor/researcher(Hossain, 2023f, 2023g). Therefore, the versatile functions and limitations of legal acts, PhD industries/universities/clinics, doctoral industries/universities/clinics, PhD students, PhD researcher, PhD supervisor, PhD violation, research misconduct, PhD misconduct, authorship in PhD research, research law, authorship law, PhD law, referee remuneration, salary of PhD/Postdoc/fellowship scholar, pension/retirement fund of PhD/Postdoc/fellowship scholar, power of attorney of PhD supervisor, authorship in research and publication, PhD, PhD (Dr.), Professor, Professor (Dr.), Scientist, and Scientist (Dr.) will be/are being remarked, opined, coalesced, and critically discussed to solve to satisfy the controversial solution in academic, profession, PhD/doctoral industries, PhD clinic, public administration, and universities. This research will be reported for the guidance support for the administrative support to chief executive officer, research scholar, professor (Dr.), PhD (Dr.), pro-vice-chancellor, vice-chancellor, and chancellor community of PhD industries and universities. Judicial counselling, academic guidance, administrative strategy, and university law will be coalesced and represented for the chancellery team of universities. A common notice will be generated for the administrative and academic to the chancellery teams to the directorial teams to the whole universities to the whole PhD industries to the whole research organizations all over the world (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ap; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) **(Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ck, 2023cl)** (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu,

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31 December 2025

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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission); applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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2023bv; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025k; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), (2026).

5.1 *Research progress, online links of publications, public intellectuals, and peer review process related research questions related to Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention of peace in PhD schooling*

Anowar Hossain's invention of camouflage physics at PhD School, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29936.23048>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286832>

Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of "Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist" on "Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds" School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

"Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)"

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>

PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8254280>

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Decision of RMIT University against Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye did a conspiracy to kill Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>

Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

31 December 2025

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
M.Tech Textile Engg (CU, India), B.Sc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australasia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. .

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574> A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>

Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles,

31 December 2025

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>

50% income support and 100% life-safety compensation were requested and proposed to Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29528.47360>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159331>

Anowar Hossain's Dream, Motivation, Research & Personal Details for attending at RMIT University whatever reported to Australian High Commissioner and Australian Visa Office whatever worked in 2018-2019. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8280942>

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

Anowar Hossain's invention for peace in PhD schooling, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286821>

"Cut the cost of defence and invest more for education" when Self-studying of a student from primary schooling to PhD schooling is an automatic contribution to national and worldwide development without getting money *Accepted in Scientific Research Publishing*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31778.20161>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242777> ;
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2831203/v1>

Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286917>

My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933678>,

My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933704>

My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3) <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966475>

Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336839>

A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195043>

31 December 2025

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
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512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>

Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com;

s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant]. School of Fashion and Textiles,

"Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)"

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21791.21922>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430696>

A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231359>

A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020) R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16273.08801>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17389964>

Letter of study leave extension for PhD research works from 1st November 2023 to 31 October 2026, designated for Md. Anowar Hossain, lecturer (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Permanent campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15384.16648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484320>

*Neuro-Camouflaging is an Indicator of Human Camouflage, an Assumption of Brain Engineering for Self-protection against Criminal Attacking. *Journal of Applied Material Science & Engineering Research*, 7(1), 67-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13401.90729>*

Referee allowance policy for writing 'letter of recommendation' and answering the questions of research employer and/or research funder <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19702.05444>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18129743>

31 December 2025

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
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<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assis. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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6 Acknowledgement

Sole author, Chief Director, PhD Research, Chief Director, Defence and Law research Centre; Chief Researcher; Textile, Color, and Material Research Centre; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023ap; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ck, 2023cl) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu, 2023bv; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bw, 2023bx, 2023by; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024y, 2024z; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024aa; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g, 2025h, 2025i, 2025k; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025) (Hossain, 2015b, 2018, 2023bq, 2023br; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), 2026); Name of Father: Late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Medical Practitioner; Permanent Residence (PR): Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); Nationality, National ID, Passport and Birth Registration Number: 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, Program Name: DR213, PhD (Fashion and Textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; Lecturer on Textile Engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar-1340, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2024(Hossain, 2023ch). Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges ‘Professor Dr. Lijing Wang’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and ‘Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks’ (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>), School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for their supervision works in the PhD school. This writing for mankind was accidentally generated during PhD journey of author at PhD school when author faced hidden life-threatening at PhD school by Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye at PhD school.

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7 Legal authorization and signing

31 December 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature (scanned)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.); Barrister (Dr.); Postdoc & PhD in Applied Law; Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology

**Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
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7.1 Research address and contact since 2020

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7.2 Permanent Address (by birth)

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Name of father: Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990),
Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh (by birth)

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile Phone: +8801788396264

31 December 2025

**Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.**

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁹ Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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8 Author contribution and authorship status of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

The author has contribution in conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

9 Declaration of conflicting interests

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11 Data availability

All data generated during the coalescing of this article are included, attached and briefly cited in reference list.

12 Caution of general readers, research funders, law implementation authorities, administrative authorities, human rights professionals, religious experts, employers, journalists, scientists, criminologists, research practitioners, professors, psychologists, educationists, relevant authorities, and relevant communities

All readers are being highly requested to understand the whole philosophy of attachments (a case report) without considering and understanding a specific word or a specific sentence or individual meaning or individual philosophy; explained for the whole meaning under the additional output of the PhD Degree in PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

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14 Self-endorsed the pictorial identification (2015-2025) of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

15 Key Glossaries

Official act of hidden life-threatening: An ethical platform of PhD schooling where unethical activities and occurrences of official life-threatening conspiracy was executed by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and officially supported by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye by silence by silence.

Family office: An office of home when professional office in PhD school was avoided due to a critical conspiracy of life-threatening, planned & chief executed by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and officially supported by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye by silence by silence.

16 For showing honour; a copy of this report is also being forwarded (randomly sequenced) to (relevant authorities may take/extend necessary action and support)

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“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
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 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
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 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
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- Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22537.62568>
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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bp). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of*

31 December 2025

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023bs). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bw). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is begging to Mr. António Guterres, the Secretary General of United Nations to stop the conflict between Gaza & Israel.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25967.41129>;
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“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author;* engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

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31 December 2025

Nobel Nominer Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
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 color engg), applied law & criminology
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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
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 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
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 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

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 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
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 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320778>
 Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* .
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 Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
 Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering,

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
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- City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>;
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Anowar

31 December 2025

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.

31 December 2025

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)
 Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT

Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion
 and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection [Biodata].*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612185>

Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author; engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>*

- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024aa). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *A follow-up communication with prime minister of Australia to alert zero responsibility of ministerial cabinet of Australia, Bangladesh, and United Nations to assess life-threatening conspiracy at RMIT, Australia.*
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18369.83044>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231359>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995119>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025c). *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16990186>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025d). *Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025e). *Local government in Bangladesh to minimize official crimes in public administration in a democratic country* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28463.85929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826808>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025f). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant].* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

31 December 2025

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice-chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission); applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.) Chief Director & Founder; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Defence Scientist; Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; RMIT</p>	<p>Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Member, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell, CU, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, BD Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; JU, BD Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Chief Researcher and Founder; Textile, Color & Material Research Centre; CU, India Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: Room-512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>

Hossain, M. A. (2025g). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching to enhance higher education and research support in Bangladesh and Australia* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32735.16801;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718630>

Hossain, M. A. (2025h). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934539>

Hossain, M. A. (2025i). *Proposal of legal acts for Australian human rights commission to high court of Australia to government of Australia to United Nations.*
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21791.21922;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430696>

Hossain, M. A. (2025j). *A research project billing of 1,00,000 BDT to City University, Bangladesh, South Asia to satisfy the project completion report (2019-2020)* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; Department of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Kolkata-700019, West Bengal, India; Department of Chemistry, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1340, Bangladesh; Email: engr.anowar@yahoo.com.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16273.08801;> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17389964>

Hossain, M. A. (2025k). *Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24765.32485;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16961335>

Hossain, M. A., Abser, M. N., & Samanta, A. K. Zero toxic approach of cotton fabric coloration with botanical waste resource via Psidium P. guajava (Guava Leaves) as natural dyes and Citrus Lemon (lemon leaves) as natural mordanting agent, submitted for publication. .
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18112.75524;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850320>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural

“Expected Position: Chief Professor/Senior Professor/Vice-Chancellor/Chancellor/Chief Scientist/Research Director (Tech)/Chief Director (R & D)”
Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain’s invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Seventh version published on 16 December 2025, 39th anniversary day of author;* engr.anowar@yahoo.com; s3820066@student.rmit.edu.au; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33291.67366>

- Finishing on Natural Fibre. *International Journal of Textile Science and Engineering*, 3(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36811.36648>
- Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A. K., NS, B., PS, V., & Shukla. (2018). Non-toxic Coloration of Cotton Fabric using Non-toxic Colorant and Nontoxic Crosslinker. *Journal of Textile Science & Engineering*, 8(5), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000374>
- Md. Anowar Hossain, A. K. S. (2019). A cost minimization process of heat and energy consumption for direct dyeing of cotton fabric coloration with triethanolamine. *Journal of Textile Engineering & Fashion Technology*, 5(5), 235-240. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>
- Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, D. S., Barrister (Dr.). (2025). *Journal of Dr. Anowar*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>
- Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain; Defence Scientist (Dr.), B. D. (2026). *Referee allowance policy for writing 'letter of recommendation' and answering the questions of research employer and/or research funder* <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19702.05444>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18129743>

Anowar

31 December 2025